

**PARENTS' INVOLVEMENT IN EDUCATION AND KEY STAGE 1 LEARNERS'
ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN AN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL: A
COMPARISON BETWEEN MODULAR DISTANCE LEARNING
AND FACE-TO-FACE EDUCATION**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 23

Issue 1

Pages: 8-27

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2137

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13208851

Manuscript Accepted: 03-11-2024

Parents' Involvement in Education and Key Stage 1 Learners' Academic Performance in an Elementary School: A Comparison Between Modular Distance Learning and Face-To-Face Education

Lenie F. Rabuyo, * Liwayway S. Viloria
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study aimed to document parents' involvement in education in relation to the academic performance of learners enrolled during the school year 2021-2023 in Gimangpang Integrated School, Initao, Misamis Oriental. Employing the explanatory-correlational research design, the data were gathered using a researcher-made questionnaire, with 117 systematic randomly selected parent respondents. Data analysis tools included descriptive statistics, paired T-test, and Pearson's product-moment correlation. Findings showed that parents were highly involved in their children's education both under modular distance learning and face-to-face education. However, the paired T-test results showed that parental involvement in education under face-to-face education was significantly higher than that under modular distance learning. Too, the academic performance of 117 randomly selected learners of the parent-respondents was significantly higher under the face-to-face education than that under modular distance learning. This implied that modular distance learning along with the threat brought about by the pandemic may have negatively influenced the academic performance of the learners under modular distance learning. However, no significant relationship existed between parental educational involvement and the academic performance of key stage 1 learners during the modular distance learning and under the face-to-face education. Findings lent evidence to the theories of zone of proximal development, behaviorism, and social cognitive.

Keywords: *parents' involvement, academic performance, modular distance learning, face-to-face education*

Introduction

The COVID-19 outbreak across the world had compelled educational institutions including the Department of Education (DepEd) to suspend face-to-face learning in order to prevent the spread of the virus. This forced the teaching community to think of new ways and alternative strategies for engaging the learners. In this light, the Department of Education had shifted to distance learning to ensure the continuity of teaching-learning processes. Subsequently, adjustments had to be made among the learners, parents, and even teachers due to new teaching and learning delivery in the new educational landscape. The traditional face-to-face learning was changed to modular distance learning in which the learners had to study independently with the help of their parents as facilitators.

Republic Act No. 9155, otherwise known as "Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001 had mandated that parents and communities shall be encouraged to actively involve in the education of children. The participation and coordination between and among the schools, the local school boards, and the Parent Teachers Associations (PTAs) must be maximized. Thus, parents instantly became teachers as they took over the role of the teacher. This had caused them anxiety, as this had interrupted with usual routine. This was one of the problems in dealing with modular distance learning as certain of the parents were not well educated. Most of them complained about this added role which had adversely affected their schedule at workplace and at home. Hence, if modular distance learning continues, it would not give a 100% achievement assurance because they are the facilitators. Yet, some of them were not well educated and some have their work. Another factor that needed to be considered was the reality that some of the parents were the ones who were answering their child's module. The unexpected turn in education provided caused by the COVID-19 pandemic brought about several challenges. This can be described both as problems in achieving learning goals and growing social equality gaps.

This sudden change had caught many families and students unaware and unprepared. It also raised concerns about increasing parental engagement and some of the deprivation. It comes with trying to please and support children in various levels and forms of distance learning. Parents' views on remote learning differ. Others feel a closer connection to their child's academic performance, while some parents see this as an additional obligation (Selwyn et al., 2011). In remote learning, parents' participation is essential. According to Brossard et al. (2020), this was meant to continue learning, but this time inside the walls of the home. Parental participation offered several benefits for students of all ages. Delgado (2017) contended that a student's family's level of involvement in their education is the best predictor of future success. Students become more motivated and grow to love learning when they sense their parents' support.

Parents in the municipality of Initao have expressed frustration about their inability to participate in their children's education, whether it be through modular distance learning or face-to-face instruction. As an example, some parents may not have known how to help their kids with their education. Others must work in the meanwhile to maintain the family's financial stability.

Such a claim suggested that parental involvement was equally crucial to children's development in the face-to-face classroom learning environment in which our educational system has just transitioned. As a result, even if it might be inferred that their educational commitment was greater through modular distance learning and their academic performance. Particularly in rural public schools like Gimangpang Integrated School, it is obvious that parents' involvement in both the epidemic and the new normal needed to be examined. This dimension of education seemed to have been less trodden in research.

Studies have proven the value of parental involvement in modular education and how it affected student's academic achievement (Morelli et al., 2020; Lim 2016; Gonzalez 2015; & Topor et al., 2010). It is crucial to thoroughly study any associations between parents' educational involvement and students' academic achievement in order to assist the learning process and learning outcomes. This research was carried out in December 2022 in order to address this specific issue.

The study was designed to determine parents' educational involvement in relation to the grades 1, 2, and 3 learners' academic performance in Gimangpang Integrated School under the modular learning modality during the pandemic and under the current face-to-face education. The researcher has been teaching for three years and seven months. By addressing such a research gap, she believed she would be able to contribute to the enhancement of the educational system and to certain educational theories and methods.

Research Questions

This study aimed to document parents' involvement in education in relation to the academic performance of grade 1, 2, and 3 learners enrolled during the school year 2021-2023 in Gimangpang Integrated School, Initao, Misamis Oriental. In particular, it attempted to answer the following questions:

1. What are the levels of involvement of parents in their children's education under modular distance learning and under the face-to-face learning approaches?
2. What are the academic performances of learners under modular distance learning and face-to-face educational approaches?
3. Is there a significant difference between the parents' educational involvement under modular distance learning and under face-to-face education?
4. Is there a significant difference between the learners' academic performance under modular distance learning and that under face-to-face education?
5. Is there significant relationship between parental educational involvement and their learners' academic performance under modular distance learning and under face-to-face education?
6. What intervention program can be crafted based on the results of the study, to level up parents' involvement in their children's education?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed an explanatory-correlational approach to research in order to determine "the extent to which two or more variables co-vary, where variance or change in one variable was reflected in variance or change in the other" (Creswell, 2012, p. 338). The questionnaire was the main method used to gather data from the selected respondents, particularly about their socioeconomic situation and the contribution of their parents' educational backgrounds to their children's academic success.

Respondents

Parent Respondents

Two categories of respondents/participants were involved in this study: the parents of currently enrolled grades 1, 2, and 3 learners and the children learners in such grade level. The parents of students in grades 1, 2, and 3 at Gimangpang Integrated School who registered during the school year (SY) 2022-2023 served as the respondents of the study. The parents of the currently enrolled kindergarten learners were not included since their children were daycare level during the previous year and because my study was limited, among others, to the currently enrolled learners and their first quarter grades during the SY 2021-2022 and 2022-2023. The respondents were chosen using a stratified random sampling technique, which involved dividing the population into homogeneous categories or within which the random sample was identified. These groups were also known as strata. This method was commonly used in combination with simple random, systematic, or cluster sampling to enhance the representativeness of a sample, thus producing a smaller sampling error (Babbie, 2001).

In this study, strata consisted of grade levels 1, 2, and 3. Two sections composed each of the grade 1 and grade 2 levels, while one section comprised grade 3. Each of these strata was considered as one stratum. Thus, random sampling was done by stratum. Using Slovin's formula, the sample size for each stratum (grade level) was determined. Simple random sampling was done within each stratum by drawing lots to select the parent respondents. A total of 117 parent respondents out of 131 parents (either the father or the mother) of grades 1, 2, and 3 learners were involved in this study. Of the parent respondents, 29 were fathers, and 88 were mothers.

Table 1. Parent Respondents by Type

Type of Parent Respondents/Grade Level	Total Population	Frequency	% To The Total Population	Percentage
Grade 1				
Father	9	8	6.11	21.6%
Mother	32	29	22.14	78.4%
Subtotal	41	37	28.24	100%

Grade 2				
Father	10	9	6.87	22%
Mother	36	32	32	78%
Subtotal	46	41	31.30	100%
Grade 3				
Father	14	12	9.16	31%
Mother	30	27	20.61	69%
Subtotal	44	39	29.77	100%
Overall Total	131	117	89.31	100%
Father	33	29	22.14	25%
Mother	98	88	67.18	75%

Respondents' Children Learners'

For the modular distance learning and for the face-to-face education, the learner respondents during the AY 2021-2022 and AY 2022-2023 were the same respondents under both learning approaches. The frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents' children learner sample size by grade level are indicated in Table 2. As with the parent respondents, the children learners involved in this study totaled 117 representing 89% of the total population.

Table 2. *Grade Levels of Respondents' Children Learners*

<i>Grade Level of Children Learners</i>	<i>Total Population</i>	<i>Sample Size</i>	<i>% to Total Population</i>
Grade 1	41	37	90
Grade 2	46	41	89
Grade 3	44	39	89
Total	131	117	89

Instruments

The questionnaire for this study was created by the researcher with the help of her advisor. Two sections made up the questionnaire. The respondents' socioeconomic profile was covered in the first section. On a four-point Likert scale, with 1 being the lowest and 4 being the highest, the parent respondents' experiences with their children's schooling were covered in the second section. The questionnaire had been validated through pilot testing and subjected to a reliability test using Cronbach's alpha. Results were posted in Table 4.

On the other hand, the academic performance of the respondents' key stage 1, 2, and 3 learners during the first semesters of AY 2021-2022 and AY 2022-2023 were obtained from the class advisers using the archival checklist. The grades of the children learners listed on the archival checklist -Table 3.

Table 3. *Academic Performance of Key Stage 1, 2, and 3 Learners During the 1st Semesters of AY 2021-2022 and AY 2022-2023*

<i>Key Stage 1 Learners</i>	<i>1st Semester AY 2021-2022</i>	<i>Remarks</i>	<i>1st Semester AY 2022-2023</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
<i>Grade 1</i>				
Learner 1	90	Passed	90	Passed
Learner 2	79	Passed	80	Passed
Learner 3	75	Passed	86	Passed
Learner 4	84	Passed	90	Passed
Learner 5	84	Passed	90	Passed
Learner 6	88	Passed	91	Passed
Learner 7	75	Passed	86	Passed
Learner 8	84	Passed	90	Passed
Learner 9	89	Passed	90	Passed
Learner 10	84	Passed	87	Passed
Learner 11	84	Passed	88	Passed
Learner 12	75	Passed	81	Passed
Learner 13	84	Passed	90	Passed
Learner 14	84	Passed	86	Passed
Learner 15	88	Passed	91	Passed
Learner 16	80	Passed	80	Passed
Learner 17	75	Passed	85	Passed
Learner 18	84	Passed	86	Passed
Learner 19	83	Passed	85	Passed
Learner 20	84	Passed	90	Passed
Learner 21	88	Passed	90	Passed
Learner 22	84	Passed	87	Passed
Learner 23	80	Passed	80	Passed

Learner 24	75	Passed	75	Passed
Learner 25	75	Passed	82	Passed
Learner 26	84	Passed	92	Passed
Learner 27	83	Passed	84	Passed
Learner 28	86	Passed	89	Passed
Learner 29	84	Passed	88	Passed
Learner 30	75	Passed	80	Passed
Learner 31	76	Passed	78	Passed
Learner 32	85	Passed	88	Passed
Learner 33	90	Passed	92	Passed
Learner 34	75	Passed	79	Passed
Learner 35	89	Passed	91	Passed
Learner 36	84	Passed	89	Passed
Learner 37	83	Passed	86	Passed
Grade 2				
Learner 1	90	Passed	90	Passed
Learner 2	86	Passed	87	Passed
Learner 3	85	Passed	91	Passed
Learner 4	85	Passed	83	Passed
Learner 5	89	Passed	89	Passed
Learner 6	84	Passed	85	Passed
Learner 7	82	Passed	83	Passed
Learner 8	85	Passed	84	Passed
Key Stage 1 Learners	1st Semester AY 2021-2022	Remarks	1st Semester AY 2022-2023	Remarks
Learner 9	89	Passed	87	Passed
Learner 10	85	Passed	85	Passed
Learner 11	88	Passed	87	Passed
Learner 12	84	Passed	86	Passed
Learner 13	89	Passed	86	Passed
Learner 14	86	Passed	87	Passed
Learner 15	83	Passed	80	Passed
Learner 16	85	Passed	87	Passed
Learner 17	83	Passed	84	Passed
Learner 18	84	Passed	84	Passed
Learner 19	85	Passed	83	Passed
Learner 20	91	Passed	93	Passed
Learner 21	85	Passed	85	Passed
Learner 22	90	Passed	91	Passed
Learner 23	86	Passed	89	Passed
Learner 24	82	Passed	82	Passed
Learner 25	80	Passed	83	Passed
Learner 26	78	Passed	80	Passed
Learner 27	75	Passed	78	Passed
Learner 28	80	Passed	83	Passed
Learner 29	83	Passed	86	Passed
Learner 30	85	Passed	89	Passed
Learner 31	90	Passed	93	Passed
Learner 32	83	Passed	83	Passed
Learner 33	75	Passed	75	Passed
Learner 34	75	Passed	76	Passed
Learner 35	85	Passed	87	Passed
Learner 36	83	Passed	85	Passed
Learner 37	89	Passed	90	Passed
Learner 38	90	Passed	93	Passed
Learner 39	80	Passed	84	Passed
Learner 40	84	Passed	86	Passed
Learner 41	90	Passed	92	Passed
Grade 3				
Learner 1	81	Passed	80	Passed
Learner 2	91	Passed	88	Passed
Learner 3	90	Passed	88	Passed
Learner 4	87	Passed	86	Passed
Learner 5	85	Passed	89	Passed
Learner 6	91	Passed	93	Passed
Learner 7	78	Passed	80	Passed

Learner 8	83	Passed	85	Passed
Learner 9	80	Passed	82	Passed
Learner 10	85	Passed	87	Passed
Learner 11	91	Passed	93	Passed
Learner 12	80	Passed	84	Passed
Learner 13	85	Passed	89	Passed
Learner 14	84	Passed	89	Passed
Learner 15	87	Passed	87	Passed
Learner 16	85	Passed	89	Passed
Learner 17	80	Passed	83	Passed
Learner 18	92	Passed	92	Passed
Learner 19	83	Passed	85	Passed
Learner 20	75	Passed	78	Passed
Key Stage 1 Learners	1st Semester AY 2021-2022	Remarks	1st Semester AY 2022-2023	Remarks
Learner 21	88	Passed	91	Passed
Learner 22	90	Passed	93	Passed
Learner 23	90	Passed	92	Passed
Learner 24	85	Passed	87	Passed
Learner 25	80	Passed	81	Passed
Learner 26	80	Passed	82	Passed
Learner 27	80	Passed	81	Passed
Learner 28	80	Passed	81	Passed
Learner 29	85	Passed	87	Passed
Learner 30	80	Passed	81	Passed
Learner 31	85	Passed	89	Passed
Learner 32	86	Passed	87	Passed
Learner 33	81	Passed	81	Passed
Learner 34	80	Passed	81	Passed
Learner 35	84	Passed	86	Passed
Learner 36	80	Passed	83	Passed
Learner 37	80	Passed	81	Passed
Learner 38	88	Passed	88	Passed
Learner 39	82	Passed	84	Passed

The pilot data revealed that the study variables had an overall Cronbach's alpha =0.8573 under the modular distance learning and 0.83 under the face-to-face education, both of which were described as good. Looking at each indicator, the Cronbach's alpha yielded results ranging from .747 or acceptable to .933 which were described, as acceptable and excellent. Respectively based on the findings, the instrument had an acceptable to excellent internal consistency indicating that the instrument was reliable and was recommended for final survey administration.

Table 4. *Reliability Statistics Result*

<i>Study Indicator</i>	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>Description</i>
Parents' Educational Involvement under Modular Distance Learning	.8573	Good
Learning Process through the Modules	.909	Excellent
Monitoring Children's learning process	.871	Good
Assessment of learning	.792	Acceptable
Parents' Educational Involvement under Face-to-Face Education	.83	Good
Learning Process through the Modules	.933	Excellent
Monitoring Children's learning process	.810	Good
Assessment of learning	.747	Acceptable

Note: Cronbach's Alpha above 0.7 was considered reliable
 ≥ 0.90 , Excellent; 0.80-0.89, Good; 0.70-0.79, Acceptable; 0.60-0.69, Questionable; 0.50-0.59, Poor; ≤ 0.49 , Unacceptable

Procedure

Necessary research protocols were observed in the administration of the survey questionnaire. In a request letter, the researcher sought permission to conduct the study from the superintendent, district supervisor, and school head of Gimangpang Integrated School at the appropriate time and place.

The researcher personally administered the survey questionnaires to the respondents to ensure a 100 percent retrieval rate. With the SPC Informed Consent Form, the respondents were made to understand the importance of the study, and that their honest answers were needed to obtain vital information on their perspectives as specified in the letter request.

The researcher herself collected the questionnaires as soon as the respondents finished them, and she personally thanked the parents for their active involvement and commitment to the study.

Data Analysis

Data processing was done upon retrieval and checking for completeness of the questionnaires. Prior to subjecting the data to statistical treatment parents' educational involvement was described in terms of the researcher-made analytical scheme shown in Table 5, using a four-point scale ranging from 4 to 1, described correspondingly as always to not at all.

On the other hand, the learners' academic performance grades were analyzed using the DepEd standards indicating five categories of descriptors namely: outstanding (grace scale (GS) = 90-100, passed); very satisfactory (GS = 85-89, passed); satisfactory (GS = 80-84, passed) fairly satisfactory (GS = 75-79, passed), and did not meet expectations (GS = below 75, failed).

Concerning the academic performance of grade 1 during the 1st quarter of SY 2021-2022, these were categorized using the analytical scheme which the researcher developed (see Table 6) based on DepEd standards shown in Table 7.

With respect to the statistical analysis of the data, the statistical tools used included descriptive statistics, Pearson's product-moment correlation, and t-test with the aid of appropriate statistical software, particularly SPSS. Frequency, percentage, weighted mean, and standard deviation were used to describe the socio-economic profile of the respondents, level of parents' educational involvement and children's academic performance. Table 5 shows the scheme for qualitatively describing the mean scores on parents' educational involvement. Prior to subjecting the data to statistical treatment parents' educational involvement was described in terms of the researcher-made analytical scheme shown in Table 5, using a four-point scale ranging from 4 to 1, described correspondingly as always to not at all.

Table 5. *Analytical Scheme for Describing Parents' Educational Involvement*

Code	Limit	Description
4	3.26 - 4.00	Always
3	2.51 - 3.25	Sometimes
2	1.76 - 2.5	Rarely
1	1.00 - 1.75	Not At All

On the other hand, the learners' academic performance grades were analyzed using the DepEd standards indicating five categories of descriptors namely: outstanding (grace scale (GS) = 90-100, passed); very satisfactory (GS = 85-89, passed); satisfactory (GS = 80-84, passed) fairly satisfactory (GS = 75-79, passed), and did not meet expectations (GS = below 75, failed).

Table 6. *Analytical Scheme for Describing Learners' Academic Performance Based on DepEd Standards for Grade 1, Grade 2, and Grade 3*

Descriptor	Grading Scale	Remarks
Outstanding	90-100	Passed
Very Satisfactory	85-89	Passed
Satisfactory	80-84	Passed
Fairly Satisfactory	75-79	Passed
Did not meet expectations	Below 75	Failed

Concerning the academic performance ratings of grade 1 during the 1st quarter of SY 2021-2022, these were categorized using the analytical scheme which the researcher developed (see Table 6) based on DepEd standards shown in Table 7.

Table 7. *Analytical Scheme for Kindergarten Learners' Academic Performance Based on DepEd Standard*

Descriptor	Grading Scale	Remarks
Consistent	85-100	Passed
Developing	75-84	Passed
Beginning	Below 75	Failed

**This grading scale is researcher-made based on DepEd Standard*

Table 8. *Rubric on Kindergarten Qualitative Academic Performance Based on DepEd Standard*

Mark	Indicator
Beginning (B) (below 75)	Rarely shows what is known correctly
	Rarely participates in class activities and work independently
	Shows interest in doing tasks but needs close supervision
Developing (D) (75-84)	Shows sometimes based on competency.
	Participates sometimes with supervision
	Continues improvement on the given task
Consistent (C) (85-100)	Expected skills are always demonstrated
	Always participates in other activities and activities by himself/herself
	Always accomplishes the given task and even a few extra tasks.

The significant differences between groups were analyzed using Paired t-test. To determine the significant relationship between parents' involvement in education and learners' academic performance under modular distance learning and in face-to-face learning, the Pearson product-moment correlation was used.

Ethical Considerations

This study was conducted in accordance with standards of behavior in research. Using the SPC Informed Consent Form, the individual respondent's voluntary involvement in this was sought prior to the administration of the questionnaire. Respondents were made to choose whether or not to participate in this study and to quit at any time without incurring any consequences. Nevertheless, none of the respondents withdrew from participating. Any discomfort, whether physical or emotional, regarding particular topics, was taken into account.

The researcher offered the respondents adequate time to complete the questionnaire. They may deliberately evaluate their viewpoints on their level of involvement in face-to-face learning during the epidemic and in modular distance learning under the new normal. The responders' information was kept private and secret. The persons' names and identities were withheld in accordance with Republic Act No. 10173 in order to preserve their anonymity.

Each author whose work was used in the research was given the necessary acknowledgment in accordance with the American Psychological Association (APA) reference standards. The researcher took care to avoid plagiarism and strictly adhere to honesty and fairness when handling the data. The research made sure that there would be no conflicts of interest during the discussion of the report. In fact, this study's conduct was conducted with rigorous adherence to the ethical standards for research.

Results and Discussion

Based on the research questions, the findings and discussions are organized in this chapter along these major areas: levels of involvement of parents in their children's education under modular distance learning and under the face-to-face learning approaches, and academic performance of learners under modular distance learning and face-to-face educational approaches.

Levels Of Parents' Involvement In Their Children's Education Under The Modular Distance Learning And Face-To-Face Education

Parents' involvement was described in terms of children's learning process, monitoring children's learning process, and assessment of learning. Each of these indicators was measured on a four-point scale with four as the highest and one as the lowest.

The involvement of parents in education had been interpreted as involvement in their children's education. It manifested itself in a variety of parental behaviors, such as their hopes for their kids' academic success, regular communication with them about the school, involvement in school events, educational activities at home, and the like. The level of parental involvement in their children's learning process, monitoring of their learning, and assessment of their learning under modular distance learning and face-to-face schooling were all scored on a four-point scale in this study. This section dealt with the findings and a discussion of this variable.

Parent's Involvement in their Children's Learning Process under the Modular Distance Learning and Face-to-Face Education

Learning is defined as "a process that leads to change, which occurs as a result of experience and increases the potential for improved performance and future learning" (Ambrose et al., 2010, p. 3). Children's learning is influenced by their parents over time. Assisting parents in the learning process helps to guarantee that kids receive the best education possible. It makes it simpler for parents and their children to develop stronger bonds. In a manner similar to this, they serve as the child's primary and ongoing educators prior to entering formal schooling and continue to have a substantial impact on their learning both inside and outside of the classroom.

Generally, findings shown in Table 9 indicated that parental involvement in their children's learning process yielded similarly high mean scores under both modular distance learning ($m=3.78\pm.19$, high involvement) and face-to-face education ($m=3.82\pm.19$, high involvement) although the latter got slightly higher mean than the former under both educational approaches. The top five mean scores ranged from 4.00-3.91. Such combined top five items that earned the five highest mean scores included the following: a) make the study area of my child at home conducive to learning ($m=4.00$, face-to-face education, ($m=3.96$, modular distance learning); b) ensure that they are physically, emotionally, and mentally ready to learn ($m=3.97$, face-to-face education); c) motivate my child to learn from the lessons ($m=3.96$, modular distance learning); d) ensure that their clothes are appropriate for studying ($m=3.94$, face-to-face education) and e) encourage my child to read the lessons regularly ($m=3.93$, face-to-face education). Face-to-face education registered the first two highest, the fourth highest, and the fifth highest while the modular distance learning obtained the third third-highest scores.

Looking at the findings under each of the two educational approaches, certain variations in level of high involvement, however, was reflected in the main scores by item. On the modular distance learning, the following items or indicators garnered top five mean scores; in descending order: a) make the study area of my child at home conducive to learning ($m=3.96$); b) motivate my child to learn from the lessons ($m=3.96$); c) encourage my child to read the lesson regularly ($m=3.91$); d) give priority time to assisting my child in learning the lesson ($m=3.83$); e) see to it that they take the right food at the right time and place ($m=3.83$); f) ensure that they are physically,

emotionally, and mentally ready to learn ($m=3.79$); and g) provide moral and spiritual guidance ($m=3.79$).

In the case of the face-to-face education, the following items obtained the top mean scores: a) make the study area of my child at home conducive to learning ($m=4.00$); b) ensure that they are physically, emotionally, and mentally ready to learn ($m=3.97$); c) ensure that their clothes are appropriate for studying ($m=3.94$); d) encourage my child to read the lesson regularly ($m=3.93$); and e) motivate my child to learn from the lesson ($m=3.88$).

Among the top five mean scores, face-to-face education garnered higher than the modular distance learning, particularly on common items mentioned earlier. Note that the items that earned top five mean scores under the face-to-face education likewise comprised the items with top mean scores under the modular distance learning, although there were slight differences, with those under the face-to-face education yielding higher mean scores. This implied that under face-to-face learning, parents had higher participation in their children's learning process, particularly in the activities with top five mean scores.

Interestingly, however, certain items emerged peculiar in terms of top five higher score to the modular distance learning in and these included the following: give priority time to assisting my child in learning the lesson; see to it that they take the food at the right time and place; and provide moral and spiritual guidance. In addition to the top five educational activities in which modular distance learning garnered similarly higher mean scores, and thus higher parental involvement, parents under this approach were likewise highly engaged in giving importance to time to assist their children in learning the lesson along with ensuring that they were fed with both material and spiritual food. Viewing this result in the light of the added educational role of parents under modular distance learning, parents had, indeed, more expanded educational participation.

With respect to the common items/indicators with lower mean scores, all of which were in the lower limit of high involvement continue for both learning modalities except for finding people who could help their children from the modular lessons when parents could not make it which obtained moderate parental involvement.

On the modular distance learning, such lower ranges of high involvement were obtained in the following items, from the lower to lowest ranges: a) assist my child perform assigned topics/activities ($m=3.76$); b) avoid or remove objects or anything that obstructs the learning process of my child ($m=3.74$); c) explain certain items or concepts in the modules/lesson to make them clear and understandable to my child ($m=3.66$); and help my child download materials to be able to understand the lesson ($m=3.59$). Overall the lower mean scores were obtained under modular distance learning, thus in terms of the learning process, parents' involvement was consistently higher in the modular distance learning in the items mentioned.

When it comes to face-to-face education, such lower ranges of high involvement were obtained in the following items, from the lower to lowest ranges: a) provide moral and spiritual guidance ($m=3.86$); b) see to it that they take the right food at the right time and place ($m=3.83$); c) give priority time to assisting my child in learning the lesson ($m=3.83$); d) assist my child to perform assigned topics/activities ($m=3.75$); e) explain certain terms or concepts in the modules/lesson to make them clear and understandable to my child ($m=3.74$); f) avoid or remove objects or anything that obstructs the learning process of my child ($m=3.73$); and g) help my child download materials to be able to understand the lesson ($m=3.66$). Generally, the lower mean scores were earned under face-to-face education, thus in terms of the learning process, parents' involvement was consistently higher in the face-to-face education in the items mentioned.

By doing simple things like asking their kids about school or helping them with their homework, parents may demonstrate to their kids that they are invested in their life, according to Chen (2021). Parents that are actively interested in their kids' education not only encourage academic success in them but also provide teachers more assurance when presenting material to assist kids learn to their maximum potential.

Table 9. *Parent's Involvement in Their Children's Learning Process under the Modular Distance Learning and Face-to-Face Education*

<i>Children's Learning Process</i>	<i>Modular Distance Learning</i>	<i>Face-to-Face Education</i>
1. Make the study area of my child at home conducive to learning.	3.96±.24 (High Involvement)	4.00±.00 (High Involvement)
2. Ensure that their clothes are appropriate for studying.	3.91±.28 (High Involvement)	3.94±.24 (High Involvement)
3. Ensure that they are physically, emotionally, and mentally ready to learn.	3.79±.41 (High Involvement)	3.97±.16 (High Involvement)
4. See to it that they take the right food at the right time and place.	3.83±.38 (High Involvement)	3.83±.38 (High Involvement)
5. Provide moral and spiritual guidance.	3.79±.41 (High Involvement)	3.86±.34 (High Involvement)
6. Avoid or remove objects or anything that obstructs the learning process of my child.	3.74±.44 (High Involvement)	3.73±.45 (High Involvement)
7. Give priority time to assisting my child in learning the lesson.	3.83±.38 (High Involvement)	3.83±.38 (High Involvement)

8. Motivate my child to learn from the lessons.	3.96±.20 (High Involvement)	3.88±.33 (High Involvement)
9. Encourage my child to read the lesson regularly.	3.91±.28 (High Involvement)	3.93±.25 (High Involvement)
10. Help my child download materials to be able to understand the lesson.	3.59±.70 (High Involvement)	3.66±.65 (High Involvement)
11. Explain certain terms or concepts in the modules/lesson to make them clear and understandable to my child.	3.66±.56 (High Involvement)	3.74±.53 (High Involvement)
12. Assist my child perform assigned topics/activities.	3.76±.43 (High Involvement)	3.75±.43 (High Involvement)
13. Find people who can help my child learn from the modules/lessons if I can't manage/understand.	3.44±.72 (Moderate Involvement)	3.49±.70 (Moderate Involvement)
	Total Measure	
	3.78±.19 (High Involvement)	3.82±.19 (High Involvement)

Note: 1.00-1.49, Never Involved; 1.50-2.49, Low Involvement; 2.50-3.49, Moderate Involvement; 3.50-4.00, High Involvement

Parent's Involvement in Monitoring Their Children's Learning Process under the Modular Distance Learning and Face-to-Face Education

Children's first teachers were their parents. The COVID-19 pandemic had emphasized the value of family support even more because parents now have to participate in front-line teaching and learning process monitoring. Their assistance had an impact on children's growth, learning, and later academic results. Parents were actively involved in watching over their children. Parents demonstrated their involvement in helping their children track the concepts they were learning.

On average, findings shown in Table 10 that parental involvement in monitoring children's learning process yielded similarly high mean scores under modular distance learning ($m=3.86\pm.22$, high involvement) and face-to-face education ($m=3.85\pm.23$, high involvement), although modular distance learning got a little higher mean score than that of face-to-face education. Covering both educational approaches, the top two mean scores ranged from 3.99 to 3.90.

The combined top two items that garnered the two highest mean scores consist of the following: a) find out whether my child focuses on his/her lessons at the scheduled time ($m=3.99$, face-to-face education, ($m=3.95$, modular distance learning), and b) check on my child's activities during his/her class schedule ($m=3.92$, face-to-face education, ($m=3.90$, modular distance learning). Face-to-face education listed was the first and the third highest while modular distance learning obtained the second and the fourth highest mean scores.

Viewing the results under the two educational approaches, some differences in the level of high involvement were remarked in the mean scores by item. In modular distance learning the following items earned the top two in descending order: a) find out whether my child focuses on his/her lessons at the scheduled time ($m=3.95$), and b) check on my child's activities during his/her class schedule ($m=3.90$).

In the event of face-to-face education, the following items earned the top mean scores: a) find out whether my child focuses on his/her lessons at the scheduled time ($m=3.99$), and b) check on my child's activities during his/her class schedule ($m=3.92$).

Among the top two mean scores, face-to-face education obtained higher than modular distance learning, primarily on the aforementioned common items. Observe that the items that gained the top two mean scores under face-to-face education along with the items of top mean scores under modular distance learning vary with those under face-to-face education yielding higher mean scores in each item. The implication was under face-to-face education parents had higher participation in monitoring children's learning process, particularly in the top two mean scores.

Concerning modular distance learning, such lower ranges of high parental involvement were obtained in the following items, from the lower to lowest ranges: a) ensure that my child is studying the right topic assigned at a particular schedule ($m=3.83$); b) ensure that my child gives priority to attending classes over non-school activities during home/school class hours ($m=3.83$); and c) follow up the learning pace of my child ($m=3.81$). Overall, the lower mean scores were obtained under modular distance learning, thus in terms of monitoring children's learning process, parents' involvement was consistently higher in the modular distance learning in the items mentioned.

In the case of face-to-face education, these lower ranges of high parental participation were found in the following items, from lower to lowest: a) ensure that my child gives priority to attending classes over non-school activities during home/school class hours ($m=3.82$); b) follow up the learning pace of my child ($m=3.79$); and c) ensure that my child is studying the right topic assigned at a particular schedule ($m=3.74$). In general, face-to-face education resulted in lower mean scores, therefore in terms of monitoring children's learning process, parental participation was consistently higher for the items in question.

As cited by Panol et al. (2021), parents are the ones who go to school to retrieve and submit modules, additional activities, and other performance tasks for their children. At home, parents helped answer the modular activities with their children and monitored their

work if all the modules were answered completely. Parents who were busy with work gave enough time to help their children answer all activities in their modules.

Table 10. *Parent's Involvement in Monitoring their Children's Learning Process under the Modular Distance Learning and Face-to-Face Education*

<i>Monitoring Children's Learning Process</i>	<i>Modular Distance Learning</i>	<i>Face-to-Face Education</i>
1. Check on my child's activities during his/her class schedule.	3.90±.30 (High Involvement)	3.92±.27 (High Involvement)
2. Find out whether my child focuses on his/her lessons at the scheduled time.	3.95±.22 (High Involvement)	3.99±.09 (High Involvement)
3. Ensure that my child gives priority to attending classes over non-school activities during home/school class hours.	3.83±.38 (High Involvement)	3.82±.38 (High Involvement)
4. Follow up the learning pace of my child.	3.81±.39 (High Involvement)	3.79±.41 (High Involvement)
5. Ensure that my child is studying the right topic assigned at a particular schedule.	3.83±.46 (High Involvement)	3.74±.44 (High Involvement)
Total Measure	3.86±.22 (High Involvement)	3.85±.23 (High Involvement)

Note: 1.00-1.49, Never Involved; 1.50-2.49, Low Involvement; 2.50-3.49, Moderate Involvement; 3.50-4.00, High Involvement

Parent's Involvement in the Assessment of Children's Learning under the Modular Distance Learning and Face-to-Face Education

In their children's general growth and education, parents are important. Given that parents were aware of and involved in their children's education, the results were remarkably positive and inspiring. As partners, home facilitators, and para-teachers, parents responsibly played a vital role in ensuring that the best holistic and educational assistance is provided. They were very focused on monitoring and supporting their children's assessments of their learning.

Generally, the findings shown in Table 11 indicated that parental involvement in the assessment of children's learning capitulated likely high mean scores under both modular distance learning ($m=3.72$, high involvement) and face-to-face education ($m=3.81$, high involvement), although they differed with higher mean scores accordingly. Both educational approaches had the top mean scores ranging from 3.97 to 3.91.

The combined top three items that obtained the three highest mean scores included the following: a) advise my child to perform the activities/tasks which the modules require ($m=3.97$, face-to-face education ($m=3.96$, modular distance learning); b) I personally assist my child to perform the tasks/activities required by the modules ($m=3.97$, face-to-face education ($m=3.95$, modular distance learning); and c) require my child to answer the questions in the modules by himself/herself ($m=3.91$, face-to-face education). Face-to-face education registered the first two highest and fourth highest while modular distance learning earned the second and third highest mean scores.

Considering the findings in each educational approach, certain variations in the level of high involvement were reflected in the mean scores by item. On the modular distance learning the following items garnered the top two mean scores in descending order: a) advise my child to perform the activities/tasks which the modules require ($m=3.96$), and b) I personally assist my child perform the tasks/activities required by the modules ($m=3.95$).

In relation to face-to-face education, the following items earned the top mean scores: a) advise my child to perform the activities/tasks which the modules require ($m=3.97$); b) I personally assist my child perform the tasks/activities required by the modules ($m=3.97$); and c) require my child to answer the questions in the modules by himself/herself ($m=3.91$).

Among the top mean scores, face-to-face education obtained higher than modular distance learning, particularly on common items mentioned earlier. With regards to the items that garnered the top two mean scores under face-to-face education likewise comprised the items with top mean scores under modular distance learning, although they have differences with those under face-to-face education yielding higher mean scores. This implied that in face-to-face education, parents had a higher engagement in the assessment of children's learning, specifically with the top mean scores.

With respect to the common items with lower mean scores, all of which were in the lower limit of high involvement continue for both learning modalities except for asking other family members, relatives, or friends to help my child accomplish the tasks/activities required by the modules and request other people to help my child answer the questions in the module if I can't manage/understand which obtained moderate parental involvement.

In modular distance learning, such lower ranges of high parental involvement were obtained in the following items, from lower to lowest ranges: a) require my child to answer the questions in the modules by himself/herself ($m=3.82$); b) explain the examination instructions to my child ($m=3.79$); c) I personally help my child answer the questions in other modules ($m=3.74$); and d) administer the quiz/examination to my child ($m=3.62$). On the whole, the lower mean scores were obtained under modular distance learning, thus

in terms of assessment of children’s learning, parents’ involvement was consistently higher in the modular distance learning in the items mentioned.

In the case of face-to-face education, such lower ranges of high parental involvement were earned in the following items from lower to lowest ranges: a) explain the examination instructions to my child (m=3.86); b) I personally help my child answer the questions in other modules (m=3.79); c) administer the quiz/examination to my child (m=3.76); d) ask other family members, relatives or friends to help my child accomplish the tasks/activities required by the modules (m=3.66); and e) request other people to help my child answer the questions in the module if I can’t manage/understand (m=3.52). Generally, face-to-face education resulted in lower mean scores, thus in terms of assessment of children’s learning, parental involvement was consistently higher for the items in question.

Table 11. *Parent’s Involvement in the Assessment of Children’s Learning under the Modular Distance Learning and Face-to-Face Education*

<i>Assessment of Children’s Learning</i>	<i>Modular Distance Learning</i>	<i>Face-to-Face Education</i>
1. Administer the quiz/examination to my child.	3.62±.55 (High Involvement)	3.76±.55 (High Involvement)
2. Explain the examination instructions to my child.	3.79±.43 (High Involvement)	3.86±.35 (High Involvement)
3. Require my child to answer the questions in the modules by himself/herself.	3.82±.41 (High Involvement)	3.91±.31 (High Involvement)
4. Advise my child to perform the activities/tasks which the modules require.	3.96±.20 (High Involvement)	3.97±.16 (High Involvement)
5. Request other people to help my child answer the questions in the module if I can’t manage/understand.	3.40±.96 (Moderate Involvement)	3.52±.86 (High Involvement)
6. Ask other family members, relatives or friends to help my child accomplish the tasks/activities required by the modules.	3.46±.97 (Moderate Involvement)	3.66±.83 (High Involvement)
7. I personally help my child answer the questions in other modules.	3.74±.48 (High Involvement)	3.79±.43 (High Involvement)
8. I personally assist my child perform the tasks/activities required by the modules.	3.95±.22 (High Involvement)	3.97±.18 (High Involvement)
Total Measure	3.72±.38 (High Involvement)	3.81±.33 (High Involvement)

Note: 1.00-1.49, Never Involved; 1.50-2.49, Low Involvement; 2.50-3.49, Moderate Involvement; 3.50-4.00, High Involvement

Consolidated Findings on Parental Involvement in Their Children’s Education Under the Modular Distance Learning and Face-to-Face Education

On the whole, the findings showed that parents were highly involved in their children’s education both under modular distance learning and face-to-face education. With a mean score of 3.78 for the former and 3.83 for the latter. These were reflected in their mean scores along the three indicators. Note, however, that overall parents’ educational involvement was slightly higher under face-to-face education than that under modular distance learning, particularly in children’s learning process (face-to-face education mean = 3.82, modular distance learning mean = 3.72) and assessment of children’s learning (face-to-face education mean = 3.81, modular distance learning mean = 3.72). It was only in monitoring children’s learning process that modular distance learning obtained a higher mean (3.86) than face-to-face education (3.85).

Table 12. *Consolidated Findings on Parental Involvement in Their Children’s Education Under the Modular Distance Learning and Face-to-Face Education*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Modular Distance Learning (MDL)</i>	<i>Face-to-Face Education (FFE)</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Children’s Learning Process	3.78±.19 (High Involvement)	3.82±.19 (High Involvement)	FFE - Higher
Monitoring Children’s Learning Process	3.86±.22 (High Involvement)	3.85±.23 (High Involvement)	MDL - Higher
Assessment of Children’s Learning	3.72±.38 (High Involvement)	3.81±.33 (High Involvement)	FFE - Higher
Total Measure	3.78±.22 (High Involvement)	3.83±.20 (High Involvement)	Face-to-face education - Higher

Looking at the findings under each educational approach, certain variations in the level of high involvement were reflected in the mean scores by indicator. On the modular distance learning each of the following indicators garnered a high mean score: a) children’s learning process (m=3.78); b) monitoring children’s learning process (m=3.86); and c) assessment of children’s learning (m=3.72).

With regards to face-to-face education, the following indicators earned high mean scores: a) children’s learning process (m=3.82); b)

monitoring children's learning process ($m=3.85$); and c) assessment of children's learning ($m=3.81$).

These results suggested that parents were more involved in their children's learning process and assessment during face-to-face instruction than they were in monitoring their progress. Parents were more heavily involved in their children's education under modular distance learning than under face-to-face instruction when it came to monitoring the learning process. This was understandable as modular distance learning involved mainly the parents and other family members in children's learners' education while the teachers were physically distant from their learners.

Academic Performances of Learner Respondents During the First Semesters of SY 2021-2022 and 2022-2023 Under the Modular Distance Learning and Face-to-Face Education

The basic thing that one gets from education is knowledge. Academic performance is the measurement of a learner's achievement across various academic subjects. It involved factors such as intellectual level, personality, motivation, skills, interests, study habits, self-esteem, or the teacher-student relationship. Meanwhile, educational success is a measure based on the academic performance of learners.

Generally, the findings shown in Table 13 highlighted that the academic performance of the learner respondents with the high mean scores under modular distance learning ($m=83.69$) and face-to-face education ($m=85.86$) with $SD=4.49$ on modular distance learning and $SD=4.31$ on face-to-face education, although the latter got slightly higher mean than the former. It implied that the academic performance of the learners' respondents, under the face-to-face education registered a higher mean than modular distance learning. This meant that the learner respondents performed better in face-to-face education than in modular distance learning.

On modular distance learning the following were academic performance ratings of the learner respondents, with 42.7% (50) of them obtaining a "satisfactory", 30.8% (36) achieved a "very satisfactory" rating, followed by 13.7% (16) of them who earned "fairly satisfactory" achievement. The least represented performance level was "outstanding", with 12.8% (15) of the children respondents. The bulk of the respondent's children earned satisfactory ratings which indicated that most of them needed to exert much more effort to achieve a much higher performance rating.

Concerning the academic performance of the respondents' learners during the face-to-face education, results revealed that 41.0% (48) of them obtained "very satisfactory" academic performance, 29.9% (35) had "satisfactory", and another 23.1% (27) achieved "outstanding". Moreover, 6.0% (7) of the respondents got "fairly satisfactory" academic performance. The bulk of the distribution clustered around "very satisfactory", followed separately by "satisfactory", and "outstanding". The least represented was "fairly satisfactory".

Comparatively, the respondents' learners had a slightly better academic performance in face-to-face education ($m=85.86$) than in modular distance learning ($m=83.69$). As shown in Table 13, the respondents' children's academic performance during modular distance learning increased particularly on the "outstanding" level (from 12.8% to 23.1%) and in the "very satisfactory" level (from 30.8% to 41.0%). By contrast, those with lower academic performance reduced: "satisfactory" levels decreased from 42.7% (50) under modular distance learning to 29.9% (35) under face-to-face education. Similarly, the "fairly satisfactory" level reduced from 13.7% (16) to 6.0% (7). The reduction in the number of learner respondents' learners who obtained lower grades and the corresponding increase in those with higher academic performance may have been brought about by certain factors under face-to-face education. This may have affected the academic performance of the learners. One of these factors may take on the form of a teaching-learning approach particularly face-to-face education. This focused on learner-centered education with support or facilitation from teachers.

Moreover, based on the result of the academic performance under modular distance learning and face-to-face education, data revealed that most of their grades were "very satisfactory" under the face-to-face education. This meant that at least, the respondents' learners developed the fundamental knowledge, skills, and core understanding, with guidance from their teacher or some peers. They can transfer learning through authentic assessment (DepEd K-12 Assessment and Rating Outcomes, 2012).

Table 13. *Academic Performances of Learner Respondents During the First Semesters of SY 2021-2022 and 2022-2023 Under the Modular Distance Learning and Face-to-Face Education*

Academic Grade	Performance Level	Modular Distance Learning		Face-to-Face Education	
		F	1st Quarter of SY 2021-2022	F	1st Quarter of SY 2022-2023
90-100	Outstanding	15	12.8	27	23.1
85-89	Very Satisfactory	36	30.8	48	41.0
80-84	Satisfactory	50	42.7	35	29.9
75-79	Fairly Satisfactory	16	13.7	7	6.0
60-74	Needs Improvement	0	0.0	0	0.0
Total		117	100.0	117	100.0
Mean		83.69		85.86	
SD		4.49		4.31	

^aBased on DepEd Standards for Grade 1, Grade 2, and Grade 3.

Significant Difference in Parents' Educational Involvement Between Modular Distance Learning and Face-To-Face Education

Parental involvement in their children's education was an excellent protective feature. They provided their children with a conducive learning environment to help them focus more on learning. Parents' role and engagement in their child's education had been heightened in which their participation was highly encouraged and anticipated.

Generally, findings shown in Table 14 revealed that there were significant differences between parental educational involvement using paired t-test analysis that yielded $t\text{-value}=-2.366^*$, $p\text{-value}=.020$ under both educational approaches.

Under each educational modality on parents' educational involvement, children's learning process and monitoring children's learning process registered to be significant results while monitoring children's learning process earned with no significant result under modular distance learning and face-to-face education. Looking at the results under each of the two educational approaches, they vary in the level of high involvement, which was reflected in the mean scores by indicators.

On the other hand, in modular distance learning, the following indicators obtained high mean scores: a) children's learning process ($m=3.78$); b) monitoring children's learning process ($m=3.86$); and c) assessment of children's learning ($m=3.72$).

In the case of face-to-face education, the following indicators garnered high mean scores: a) children's learning process ($m=3.82$); b) monitoring children's learning process ($m=3.85$); and c) assessment of children's learning ($m=3.81$).

Note that the indicators that earned high mean scores under face-to-face education likewise comprised the indicators with high mean scores under modular distance learning, although they vary slightly with those on face-to-face education yielding higher mean scores. This implied that face-to-face education had higher participation than modular distance learning.

With respect to the common indicators of parents' educational involvement under modular distance learning and face-to-face education the following were the results of paired t-test: a) children's learning process with $t\text{-value}=-2.345^*$, $p\text{-value}=.021$, which indicated significant differences in parents' educational involvement between the two educational settings, b) monitoring children's learning process with $t\text{-value}=.372\text{ns}$, $p\text{-value}=.710$, suggesting a significant difference in parental involvement between the two educational settings, and c) assessment of children's learning with $t\text{-value}=-3.645^{**}$, $p\text{-value}=.000$, indicating a significant difference in parents' involvement. Viewing the result at the key variable level, the paired t-test result showed that there was a significant difference in the parental involvement between the modular distance learning and face-to-face education with the $t\text{-value}=-2.366^*$, $p\text{-value}=.020$.

These findings were consistent with previous research, such as a study by Ziegler and Hagelskamp (2019), which found that parental involvement was lower in online distance learning compared to traditional classroom-based learning. Similarly, Law and Chow (2020) found that parental involvement played a critical role in students' online learning experience and academic achievement.

On the contrary, the insignificant difference in parental involvement in monitoring children's learning process between the two educational approaches was contradictory to the finding of a study by Wang et al. (2019), which showed that parents were more involved in monitoring their children's learning progress in online distance learning than in traditional classroom-based learning.

The significant differences in parental involvement in the learning process and assessment of learning between modular distance learning and face-to-face education. It suggested that educators and policymakers should encourage and support parental involvement in online learning to enhance students' academic performance. To achieve this, regular communication channels between parents and teachers, parent education programs, and resources to facilitate parental involvement in the online learning process should be provided (Ziegler & Hagelskamp, 2019).

Table 14. *Significant Difference in Parents' Educational Involvement Between Modular Distance Learning and Face-To-Face Education*

Indicator	Modular Distance Learning	Face-to-Face Education	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Children's Learning Process	3.78±.19 (High Involvement)	3.82±.19 (High Involvement)	-2.345*	.021	Significant
Monitoring Children's Learning Process	3.86±.22 (High Involvement)	3.85±.23 (High Involvement)	.372ns	.710	Not significant
Assessment of Children's Learning	3.72±.38 (High Involvement)	3.81±.33 (High Involvement)	-	.000	Significant
Total Measure	3.78±.22 (High Involvement)	3.83±.20 (High Involvement)	-2.366*	.020	Significant

Note: Analysis is based Paired t-test *significant ($p<.05$) **significant ($p<.01$) ns-not significant($p>.05$)

Relationship Between Parental Educational Involvement And Their Children's Academic Performance Under The Modular Distance Learning And Face-To-Face Education

The Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient or Pearson's was used to determine whether parental educational involvement had a relationship with their children's academic success in both modular distance learning and face-to-face schooling. The three measures of parental educational involvement, such as children's learning, did not significantly relate to one another, according to analysis of the

correlational test displayed in Table 17. Similarly, parental educational involvement was insignificantly related to children's academic performance.

Relationship Between Parental Educational Involvement and Their Children's Academic Performance Under the Modular Distance Learning

Parenting amid a pandemic had been challenging. The COVID-19 pandemic prompted the temporary suspension of face-to-face classes and the transition to a modular print distance learning method. It was said that parenting in times of pandemic was fundamentally the reconstruction from scratch.

On the whole, the results of the correlation test between parental educational involvement and their children's academic under modular distance learning using Pearson's product-moment correlation analysis were posted in Table 15. The test did not yield a significant relationship between parental educational involvement and the children's academic performance of the learners' respondents. None of the indicators was significantly related to academic performance under modular distance learning ($p > .05$). In short, parental educational involvement and the children's academic performance had no significant association under modular distance learning. This implied that parental educational involvement did not have a significant influence on the children's academic performance during the normal situation before the pandemic when the conventional modular distance learning method was used.

On the other hand, the following indicators showed that there was likewise no significant relationship between modular distance learning and face-to-face education on children's learning process (r -value=.032ns, p -value=.735), monitoring of children's learning process (r -value=0.88ns, p -value=.347), and assessment of children's learning process (r -value=.134ns, p -value=.149).

Moreover, this may mean that most of the respondents' learners in Gimangpang Integrated School may have experienced certain difficulties that interfered with their learning process. Although the bulk of the respondents obtained "satisfactory" (42.7%) academic performance under modular distance learning, parental educational involvement could not be accounted for the children's academic performance under modular distance learning.

These findings were consistent with previous studies that have reported weak or non-significant correlations between parental involvement and learners' academic performance in online learning environments (Wang et al., 2019). However, it was important to note that parental involvement can still have a positive impact on learners' academic performance through other means, such as providing emotional support, creating a conducive home environment for learning, and helping with time management and organization (Deslandes & Royer, 2019).

Table 15. *Relationship Between Parental Educational Involvement and Their Children's Academic Performance Under the Modular Distance Learning*

Indicator	Learners' Academic Performance		Remarks
	<i>r</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value	
Children's Learning Process	.032ns	.735	Not significant
Monitoring of Children's Learning Process	.088ns	.347	Not significant
Assessment of Children's Learning	.134ns	.149	Not significant

Note: Analysis is based on Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation ns-not significant ($p > .05$)

Relationship Between Parental Educational Involvement and their Children's Academic Performance under Face-to-Face Education

Parental involvement in the learning activities of their children and the perceived impact of parents on their children's achievement was of continuing interest to educators as they were trying to find ways to improve the academic achievement of their learners. Parent involvement in a child's education was consistently found to be positively associated with a child's academic performance.

Specifically, the findings shown in Table 16 indicated that there was a lack of significant relationship between parental educational involvement and their children's academic performance under face-to-face education. The indicators under parental involvement and academic performance did not significantly correlate with the academic performance under face-to-face education ($p > .05$). In short, the data did not provide evidence that parental educational involvement may have influenced the academic performance of the learners' respondents under face-to-face education.

In particular, the following indicators showed that there were no significant relationships between parental educational involvement and children's learning process (r -value=-.006ns, p -value=.949), monitoring children's learning process (r -value=.018ns, p -value=.849), and assessment of children's learning (r -value=-.103ns, p -value=.267), both under modular distance learning and face-to-face education.

While the favorable influence of parental educational involvement on children's academic performance may be assumed as a trend, it was different in the case of the learners' respondents in Gimangpang Integrated School under both learning modalities. There could be some factors that may have affected the academic performance of the learners' respondents. As the findings of this study showed, the "very satisfactory" academic performance of the learners' respondents were possibly a result of their favorable family environment and academic enthusiasm. However, the lack of a significant relationship between parental educational involvement between children's

academic performance may be attributed to other factors.

These findings were consistent with previous research that was shown that parental involvement in education was not always a predictor of academic performance (Flouri & Buchanan, 2003; Hill & Tyson, 2009). This might be because the link between parental participation and academic success is complicated. Numerous variables, including financial situation, parental education level, and cultural background, had an impact on this (Fan & Chen, 2001). Although the results suggested that parental educational involvement may not be a strong predictor of academic performance under face-to-face education, it was still important for educators and policymakers to encourage and facilitate parental involvement in their children's education. This can lead to positive outcomes such as increased student motivation, improved behavior, and better school attendance (Desforges & Abouchaar, 2003).

Table 16. Relationship Between Parental Educational Involvement and their Children's Academic Performance under Face-to-Face Education

Indicator	Learners' Academic Performance		Remarks
	r-value	p-value	
Children's Learning Process	-.006ns	.949	Not significant
Monitoring Children's Learning Process	.018ns	.849	Not significant
Assessment of Children's Learning	-.103ns	.267	Not significant

Legend: Analysis was based on Pearson's product-moment correlation ns- means not significant (p>.05) α= 0.05

Consolidated Findings on Relationship Between Parental Educational Involvement and Their Learners' Academic Performance

It has long been believed that parents played a crucial role in their children's academic success. A child's academic development was basically influenced by parent-child interactions, particularly stimulating and attentive parenting techniques. Numerous criteria had been used to define and rate parent engagement. Parents' behaviors both at home and at school, as well as their attitudes regarding their children's education, the educational setting in which they were educated, and their teachers, were among these factors.

Showcasing the comparative scenarios of the relationship between parental educational involvement and their children's academic performance under modular distance learning and face-to-face education were the Pearson's analysis results shown in Table 17. As posted, the relationship between parental involvement and children's academic performance was insignificant. These may be attributed to the sampling error and some non-sampling factors that have affected the academic performance of the children, such as the teaching styles of the teachers, the sudden shift of teaching methods, the emotional support of the parents, and the like.

There were differences in children's academic achievement between the parental engagement profiles, according to Lara and Saracosti's 2019 study, which looked at parental involvement in education and kids' academic achievement. It was discovered that kids' academic performance was lower when their parents weren't as interested in their schooling. However, these results did not demonstrate a connection between parental involvement in a child's schooling and that child's academic success.

Table 17. Pearson's Analysis of Relationship Between Parental Educational Involvement and Their Children's Academic Performance Under Modular Distance Learning and Face-to-Face Education

Indicator	Parental Educational Involvement		Modular Distance Learning				Face-to-Face Education			
	MDL	FFE	Academic Performance	r-value	p-value	Remarks	Academic Performance	r-value	p-value	Remarks
Children's Learning Process	3.78±.19	3.82±.19	83.69	.032ns	.735	Not Significant	85.86	-.006ns	.949	Not Significant
Monitoring Children's Learning Process	3.86±.22	3.85±.23		.088ns	.347	Not Significant		.018ns	.849	Not Significant
Assessment of Learning	3.72±.38	3.81±.33		.134ns	.149	Not Significant		-.103ns	.267	Not Significant

Legend: MDL: Modular Distance Learning FFE: Face-to-Face Education

Conclusions

Based on the findings and analysis of the study, certain conclusions were drawn.

Parents' involvement in children's education significantly differed under modular distance learning and under face-to-face education, with parents' involvement in face-to-face as better than their involvement in modular distance learning. This can be inferred from the findings on children's learning process, monitoring children's learning progress, and assessment of children's learning. The pandemic situation might have negatively influenced the parents' educational involvement under the modular distance learning. Similarly, a significant difference existed between the academic performance of the respondents under modular distance learning and during face-to-face learning, with the academic performance under face-to-face learning being higher than that under the modular distance learning. However, parents' involvement did not yield significant relationship with their children's academic performance both during pandemic

and during face-to-face learning.

Findings have lent credence to Vygotsky's zone of proximal development theory which argued that there was an area in child's development where their individual independent capacity to solve problem existed and a space or concern where they needed the guidance and assistance from an adult such as parents at home and teachers in school. Thus, such a social space or context must be adequately addressed by the appropriate social environment such as the parents or other capable family members at home and the teachers in school if a desired child development must be achieved. This particular kind of social environment was more likely to exist in a face-to-face education where teachers could directly facilitate learning in school, while parents or other capable family members at home could personally provide educational guidance and assistance at home.

This study has provided empirical evidence to such an assumption in child's development as reflected in the significantly higher parental educational involvement under the face-to-face education than under the modular distance learning. This was further reinforced by the significantly better academic performance of learners under the face-to-face education compared to that under modular distance learning.

However, the absence of significant relationship between the parents' educational involvement and their children's academic performance in both modular distance learning and face-to-face education calls for a reasonable explanation. Aside from sampling error, possible explanation may be sourced out from some non-sampling errors which were beyond the scope of the present study. As Bandura's social cognitive theory emphasized, learning occurred in a social setting characterized by a dynamic interaction between the individual, the behavior, and the social settings where a person's learning took place and where he/she practiced his/her behavior. Learning, thus resulted from a process of social influence. Parents' educational involvement alone or singly may not be accounted for their children's academic performance. Moreover, this theory had given importance to both internal and external reinforcement, especially positive ones, which may emerge from the individual's social context, including the family, school, peers and even other people or groups.

Based on the findings, conclusions, and limitations of the study, the following recommendations are set forth in three categories.

Areas for Future Research

Future studies that combine qualitative and quantitative research approaches are needed to examine the connection between parents' involvement and learners' academic performance.

Future research may replicate this study in other settings to find out whether or not such would yield similar results.

Future researchers may use this study as a foundation for determining the potential most effective methods for parents to influence their children's learning process and academic achievement.

Future research may replicate this study but expanded in terms of sample covering all schools in Initao South District.

Policy Review/Action

In order to improve parental involvement with their children's education, the Department of Education must sustain the current educational policies as the foundation for developing and implementing appropriate intervention programs or activities.

Teachers and school administrators must enhance policies and strategies to develop parents' approaches to help their children improve their academic performance.

The Department of Education must prolong various activities that will engage parents in their children's academic pursuits.

Practical Utilization of Findings

To enhance learners' academic performance, the Department of Education of Initao South District must keep up and expand such resources that may be conveniently accessed by learners during the teaching-learning process.

Teachers must encourage parents to improve the learning environment in their homes.

Teachers must conduct home visits regularly to assess the progress of the academic performance of the learners.

References

- Aguirre, V. (2020). Using Vibal mdl materials: A walkthrough and practical reminders for teachers and parents. file:///C:/Users/windows%2010/Downloads/1001001520223116.pdf.
- Ali, N. A., Bhamani, N., Bharuchi, S., Kaleem, V. S., & Makhdoom, A. (2020). Home learning in times of COVID: Experiences of parents. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1259928.pdf>.
- Ali, R., Ghazi, S. R., Khan, M. S., Hussain, S., & Faitma, Z. T. (2010). Effectiveness of modular teaching in biology at secondary level. *Asian Social Science*, 6(9). <https://doi.org/10.5539/ass.v6n9p49>.

- Alghazo, Y. (2016). Framework for narrowing the achievement gaps. <https://www.ijer.net/archive/v5i4/NOV162664.pdf>.
- Al-Mahrooqi, R., Denman, C., & Al-Maamari, F. (2016). Omani parents' involvement in their children's English education. *SAGE Open*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244016629190>
- Altschul, I. (2011). Parental involvement and the academic achievement of Mexican American youths: what kinds of involvement in youths' education matter most? *Social Work Research*, Volume 35, Issue 3, September 2011, Pages 159–170, <https://doi.org/10.1093/swr/35.3.159>.
- Ambayon, E. (2020). Modular-based approach and student's achievement in literature. *International Journal of Education and Literary Studies*, 8 (3). <https://doi.org/10.7575/aiac.ijels.v.8n.3p.32>.
- Ambrose, S., Bridges, M., DiPietro, M., Lovett, M., & Norman, M. (2010). *How learning works: Seven research-based principles for smart teaching*. San Francisco: JosseyBass.
- Babbie, E. (2001). *The practice of social research*. 9th Edition, Wadsworth Thomson, Belmont.
- Bagnato, S. (2007). *Authentic assessment for early childhood intervention: Best practices*. New York: Guilford.
- Bandura, A. (1986). *Social foundations of thought and action: A social cognitive theory*. <http://www.uky.edu/~eushe2/Bandura/Bandura1989ACD.pdf>.
- Basa, G. (2020). Parents empowerment: Exercising their power as co Educators in the new normal. Vibal group (Facebook group).
- Bhamani, S., Makhdoom, A. Z., Bharuchi, V., Ali, N., Kaleem, S., & Ahmed, D. (2020). Home learning in times of COVID: Experiences of parents. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*, 7(1). <http://dx.doi.org/10.22555/joeed.v7i1.3260>.
- Bendijo, A. (2020). New normal: How parents embrace the challenges in education. <https://www.depedmalaybalay.net/articles/new-normal-how-parents-embrace-the-challenges-in-education.html>.
- Bernard, H. (1990). *Psychology of learning and teaching*. https://www.academia.edu/25997693/Influence_of_Study_Habits_on_Academic_Performance_of_Junior_High_School_Students_in_the_Gomoa_West_District_of_Ghana.
- Bernardo, J. (2020). Modular learning most preferred parents: DepEd. ABS-CBN news. <https://news.abs-cbn.com/news/07/30/20/modular-learning-most-preferred-by-parents-deped>.
- Brooks, A. (2019). Experts discuss the importance of positive parental involvement in education. <https://www.rasmussen.edu/degrees/education/blog/parental-involvement-in-education/>.
- Brossard, M., Cardoso, M., Kamei, A., Mishra, S., Mizunoya, S., & Reuge, N. (2020). Parental Engagement in Children's Learning. <https://www.unicef-irc.org/publications/1091-parental-engagement-inchildrens-learning.html>
- Chen, G. (2021). Parental involvement is key to student success. *Public School Review*. <https://www.publicschoolreview.com/blog/parental-involvement-is-key-to-student-success>
- Choi, N., Chang, M., Kim, S., & Reio Jr, T. G. (2015). A structural model of parent involvement with demographic and academic variables. *Psychology in the Schools*, 52 (2), 154-167. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/pits.21813>
- Creswell, J. (2012). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative research*. 4th edition. Pearson.
- Dargo, J. M., & Dimas, M. (2021). Modular distance learning: Its effect in the academic performance of learners in the new normal. *JETL (Journal of Education, Teaching, and Learning)*, 6(2), 204-208.
- Delgado, P. (2017). The importance of parental involvement in teaching. <https://ob-servatory.tec.mx/edu-news/the-importance-of-parental-involvement-in-teaching>
- Department of Education (2012). K to 12 assessment and rating outcomes. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2012/09/05/do-73-s-2012-guidelines-on-the-assessment-and-rating-of-learning-outcomes-under-the-k-to-12-basic-education-curriculum/>.
- Department of Education (2015). Adopting the indigenous people's education curriculum framework. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2015/07/29/do-32-s-2015-adopting-the-indigenous-peoples-education-curriculum-framework/>.
- Department of Education (2019). *Alternative learning system education and skills training handbook for implementers*. https://www.deped.gov.ph/als-est/PDF/ALS-EST_Handbook_for_Implementers.pdf.
- Desforges, C., & Abouchaar, A. (2003). *The impact of parental involvement, parental support and family education on pupil achievements and adjustment: A literature review*. London: Department for Education and Skills.
- Deslandes, R., & Royer, E. (2019). Parental involvement in online learning: Insights from a systematic literature review. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 16(1), 39.

- Dewarle, J. (2014). Parent-teacher collaboration: Sharing knowledge to support a child's literacy development. A project submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Master of Education in Special Education. Vancouver Island University, Nanaimo, British Columbia.
- Epstein, J. L., & Sheldon, S. B. (2019). Evaluate programs of partnership: Critical considerations. J. L. Epstein (Eds) *School, family, and community partnerships: Your handbook for action* (pp. 323-359). Thousand Oaks, CA: Corwin.
- Erdener, M.A., & Knoepfel, R.C. (2018). Parents' perceptions of their involvement in schooling. *International Journal of Research in Education and Science (IJRES)*, 4(1), 1-13. DOI:10.21890/ijres.369197.
- Fan, X., & Chen, M. (2001). Parental involvement and students' academic achievement: A meta-analysis. *Educational Psychology Review*, 13(1), 1-22. Firmanto, A., Sumarsono, P., & Nur, F. (2020). A family-school partnership based learning: An effort to organize early childhood education during pandemic. In *International Conference on Community Development (ICCD 2020)* (pp. 100-103). Atlantis Press. <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.201017.023>.
- Flouri, E., & Buchanan, A. (2018). What predicts parental involvement with their child's education? *Journal of Education and Psychology*, 23(4), 417-434.
- Gonzales, E. (2015). a modular approach utilizing decision tree in teaching integration techniques in calculus. Department of Arts, Sciences and Teacher Education, City College of Calamba, Calamba City, Laguna, Philippines.
- Hancı-Azizoğlu, E., & Kavaklı, N. (2021). Rewriting the future through rhetorical technology. In E. B. Hancı-Azizoğlu, & N. Kavaklı Ulutaş (Eds.), *Futuristic and Linguistic Perspectives on Teaching Writing to Second Language Students* (pp. 1-15). IGI Global, 2021
- Harris, A. & Goodall, J. (2007). Engaging parents in raising achievement: Do parents know they matter? Research Report DCSF-RW004. University of Warwick. Department for Children, Schools and Families.
- Hill, N. E., & Craft, S. A. (2003). Parent-school involvement and school performance: Mediated pathways among socioeconomically comparable African American and Euro-American families. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 95(1), 74-83. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0663.95.1.74>.
- Hill, N. E., & Tyson, D. F. (2009). Parental involvement in middle school: A meta-analytic assessment of the strategies that promote achievement. *Developmental Psychology*, 45(3), 740-763.
- Hill, N. E., Witherspoon, D. P., & Bartz, D. (2018). Parental involvement in education during middle school: Perspectives of ethnically diverse parents, teachers, and students. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 111 (1), 12-27. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220671.2016.1190910>.
- Ho, E. (2009). Educational leadership for parental involvement in an Asian context: Insights from Bourdieu's Theory of practice. *The School Community Journal*. Vol.19, No.2.
- Hoover-Dempsey, K.V., & Sandler, H. M. (2005). Final performance report for OERI grant # R305T010673: The social context of parental involvement: A path to enhanced achievement. Paper presented to Project Monitor, Institute of Education Sciences, U.S. Department of Education.
- Jaiswal, S. (2017). Role of parental involvement and some strategies that can promote parental involvement. *Journal of International Academic Research for Multidisciplinary*, 5(2), 95-104.
- Kalaycı, G. & Oz, H. (2018). Parental involvement in English language education: Understanding parents' perceptions. *International Journal of Teaching & Education*. 5. 832-847.
- Keith, K. (2020). How parents can become more involved in schools. <https://www.verywellfamily.com/parent-involvement-in-schools-619348#citation-1>.
- Kendler, J. (1995). *Basic psychology*. (3rd ed.). W. A. Benjamin Inc. https://www.academia.edu/25997693/Influence_of_Study_Habits_on_Academic_Performance_of_Junior_High_School_Students_in_the_Gomoa_West_District_of_Ghana.
- Kerr, M.L., Rasmussen, H.F., Fanning, K.A. & Braaten, S.M. (2021). Parenting during COVID-19: A study of parents' experiences across gender and income levels. *Fam Relat*, 70: 1327-1342. <https://doi.org/10.1111/fare.12571>.
- Kimu, A. (2012). Parent involvement in public primary schools in Kenya, University of South Africa, Pretoria. <http://hdl.handle.net/10500/6031>
- Kwatubana, S.J. & Makhalemele, T.J. (2015). Parental involvement in the process of implementation of the national school nutrition program in public schools. *International Journal of Educational Sciences*, 9(3):315-323. [<http://www.krepublishers.com/02-Journals/IJES/IJES-00-0-000-000-2009-Web/IJES-00-0-000-000-2009-1-Cover.htm>].

- LeBrun, D. (2001). A study of modularized instruction and its role in the technology education curriculum at Southern Door Schools. The Graduate College University of Wisconsin-Stout.
- Llego, A. (2020). DepEd learning delivery modalities for school year 2020-2021. TeacherPH. Professional Learning Online community. For Teachers and of the Teacher.
- Lara, L. & Saracosti, M. (2019). Effect of parental involvement on children's academic achievement in Chile. <https://www.frontiersin.org/arti-cles/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.01464/full>.
- LaRocque, M., Kleiman, I., & Darling, S.M. (2011). Parental involvement: the missing link in school achievement. *Preventing School Failure: Alternative Education for Children and Youth*, 55(3), 115–122. doi:10.1080/10459880903472876.
- Law, N., & Chow, A. (2020). Parental involvement, self-regulated learning, and academic achievement of K-12 students in online learning environments. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 58(2), 388-406.
- Lebaste, V. (2020). The role of parents in modular distance learning. <https://www.pressreader.com/philippines/su.nstarpampang/20201128/281681142436238>.
- Lim, E. (2016). Effectiveness of modular instructions in word problem solving of BEED students. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Effectiveness-of-Modular-Instruction-in-WordofLim/fb67>.
- Liu, F., Black, E., Algina, J., Cavanaugh, C., & Dawson, K. (2010). The validation of one parental involvement measurement in virtual schooling. *Journal of Interactive Online Learning*, 9(2), 105–132.
- Magsambol, B. (2020). 8.8 million parents prefer modular learning for students –DepEd. <https://rappler.com/nation/deped-says-parents-prefer-modular-learning-students>.
- Mahmoud, S. (2018). Saudi parents' perceptions of the kind of help they offer to their primary school kids. *English Language Teaching*, 11(3), 102-112.
- Makrooni, G. (2019). Being a first-generation migrant family student in finland: perceptions and experiences of the educational journey to higher education. *Journal of Ethnic and Cultural Studies*, 6(3), 157-170. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.29333/ejecs/293>
- Malipot, M. (2020). DepEd: Most students prefer 'modular' learning over online. *Manila Bulletin*. <https://mb.com.ph/2020/07/03/deped-most-students-prefer-modular-learning-o>.
- Manila Times. (2020). Crucial role parents play in children's continuous learning. Author. <https://www.manilatimes.net/2020/07/30/campus-press/crucial-roleparents-play-in-childrens-continuous-learning/747924/>.
- Manlangit, P., Paglumotan, A. M., & Sopera, S. C. (2020). Supercharging Filipino parents is key for successful modular distance learning. <https://www.flipsience.ph/news/features-news/tagapagdaloy-modulardistancelearning/#:~:text=Modular%20learning%20is%20a%20form,%20and%20studever-online/>.
- Morelli, M., Cattelino, E., Baiocco, R., Trumello, C., Babore, A., Candelori, C., & Chirumbolo, A. (2020). Parents and children during the COVID-19 lockdown: The influence of parenting distress and parenting self-efficacy on Children's Emotional Well-Being. *Front. Psychol.*, 06 October 2020 Sec. Health Psychology <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.584645>.
- Nagle, R. (2007). Issues in preschool assessment. In *Psychoeducational assessment of preschool children*. Edited by B. A. Bracken and R. J. Nagle, 29–48. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Nicdao, A. (2020). The importance of stronger parent-teacher collaboration in the new normal education. *Master Teacher I, Casupanan Elementary School Volume 11, No. 1 (2020)*.
- Niehaus, K., & Adelson, J. L. (2014). School support, parental involvement, and academic and social-emotional outcomes for English language learners. *American Educational Research Journal*, 51(4), 810-844.
- Nihat, S., Gürbüztürk, O. (2013). Primary school students' parents' level of involvement into their children's education. *Educational Sciences: Theory & Practice*, 13(2) Educational Consultancy and Research Center. www.edam.com.tr/estp.
- Onocha, C., & Okpala, P. (1985). Family and environmental correlates of science achievement of pupils in primary schools. *Journal of Science Teachers Association of Nigeria*, 23, 1725.
- Oxford Learning. (2018). Fighting for focus: How to help your child focus in school (and at home). <https://www.oxfordlearning.com/how-to-help-child-focus-in-school/>
- Panol, R., Caballes, D., Javillonar, M., Vasquez, A., & Vasquez, M. (2021). Parental involvement in students' completion of learning tasks in Science. *International Journal of Scientific Research*, 7(5), 1-7. https://www.isroset.org/journal/IJSRMS/full_paper_view.php?paper_id=2382#parentHorizontalTab3.

- Pimentel, J. (2020). The new normal in basic education. *Lexology*. <https://www.lexology.com/library/detail.aspx?g=f4c146a9-7ef0-4bc1-8d6d-e6516a4a14ff>.
- Reininger, T. (2014). Parental involvement in municipal schools in Chile: Why do parents choose to get involved? Ph.D. Dissertation, Fordham University Graduate School of Social Service, New York, NY
- Rudnitsky, A. (2011). *Course design: A guide to curriculum development for teachers*. New York: Longman
- Sadiq, S. (2014). Effectiveness of modular approach in teaching at university level. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 8.
- Salandakan, G. (2019). *Teacher education*. QC, KATHA Publishing Co., Inc.
- Sapungan, G., & Sapungan, R. (2014). Parental involvement in child's education: importance, barriers and benefits. *Asian Journal of Management Sciences & Education*, 3(2).
- Seale, C. (2020). Parent involvement has always mattered. Will the COVID-19 pandemic finally make this the new normal in K-12 education? *Forbes*. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/colinseale/2020/05/19/parent-involvement-has-always-mattered-will-the-covid-19-pandemic-finally-make-this-the-new-normal-in-k-12-education/?sh=4f84acbe5e46>.
- Sejpal, K. (2013). Modular method of teaching. *International Journal for Research in Education*. Vol. 2, Issue:2, February 2013 (IJRE) ISSN:2320-091X
- Selwyn, N., Banaji, S., Hadjithoma-Garstka, C., & Clark, W. (2011). Providing a platform for parents? Exploring the nature of parental engagement with school learning platforms. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 27(4), 314-323. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2729.2011.00428.x>.
- Skinner, B. F. (1938). *The behavior of organisms: An experimental analysis*. New York: Appleton-Century-Crofts. <https://education.stateuniversity.com/pages/2421/Skinner-B-F-1904-1990.html#ixzz7jUKIw2gF>.
- Topor, D., Keane, S., Shelton, T. & Calkins, S. (2010). Parent involvement and student academic performance: A multiple mediational analysis. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articcles/PMC3020099/>
- Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in society: The development of higher psychological processes*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Wang, Q., Chen, L., & Liang, Y. (2019). A meta-analysis of the effects of parental involvement on students' academic achievement in online learning. *Distance Education*, 40(3), 1-19.
- Wang, Y., Chen, N., Liang, C., & Zhou, X. (2019). Parental involvement in children's online learning: A review of empirical research. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 2478.
- Wang, G., Zhang, Y., Zhao, J., Zhang, J., & Jiang, F. (2020). Mitigate the effects of home confinement on children during the COVID-19 outbreak. *The Lancet*, 395(10228), 945-947. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(20\)30547-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30547-X).
- White, S. (2018). Importance of parental involvement in education. <https://din-nertablemba.com/importance-of-parental-involvement-in-education/>.
- Woofter, S. (2019). Book review: Building equity: Policies and practices to empower all learners. *American Journal of Qualitative Research*, 3(1), 136-139. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ajqr/5815>.
- Zainuddin, Z., Perera, C.J., Haruna, H. & Habiburrahim, H. (2020). Literacy in the new norm: stay-home game plan for parents. *Information and Learning Sciences*, Vol. 121 No. 7/8, pp. 645-653. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ILS-04-2020-0069>.
- Zhao, Y., Guo, Y., Xiao, Y., Zhu, R., Sun, W., Huang, W., & Wu, J. L. (2020). The effects of online homeschooling on children, parents, and teachers of grades 1-9 during the COVID19 pandemic. *Medical Science Monitor: International Medical Journal of Experimental and Clinical Research*, 26, e925591-1.
- Ziegler, A., & Hagelskamp, C. (2019). The involvement of parents in the school education of their children: A comparison of traditional classroom and online distance learning. *Journal of Educational Research Online*, 11(1), 187-205.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Lenie F. Rabuyo

Gimangpang Integrated School – Philippines

Liwayway S. Viloría, PhD

St. Peter's College – Philippines